

Lavender

Attribute	Description	Reference
Lavender-ID	Overall intensity of lavender oil substitute	Fresh lavender - 10.0 Lavender Insect Repellent - 5.0
Floral notes	Scent reminiscent of various flowers	Pure rose essential oil - 9.0 Rose petals - 4.0
Freshness	Scent giving clean, fresh sensation	Air freshener - 10.0 Fresh laundry - 5.0
Green notes	Grassy, fresh vegetables, possible slightly herbal, earthy associated scents	Freshly cut grass - 10.0 Herbal tea - 4.0
Sweetness	Pleasant and sugary scent	Honey - 9.0 Vanilla ice-cream - 5.0
Spiciness	Spicy, sharp scent, peppery notes	Cayenne - 9.0 Dried ginger - 5.0
Woody notes	Brown, more/less heavy, warm scent	Wet firewood - 9.0 Pencil shavings - 5.0
Camphoraceous notes	Sharp and cooling, medicine like notes, menthol/camphor like	Menthol vapor rub - 8.0 Eucalyptus candy - 4.0
Citrus notes	Scent reminiscent of various citrus (lemons, oranges, grapefruit etc.)	Fresh citrus peels - 9.0 Lemonade - 4.0

Citrus

Attribute	Description	Reference
Citrus-ID	Overall intensity of citrus oil substitute	Fresh lavender - 10.0 Lavender Insect Repellent - 5.0
Floral notes	Scent reminiscent of various flowers	Pure rose essential oil - 9.0 Rose petals - 4.0
Freshness	Scent giving clean, fresh sensation	Air freshener - 10.0 Fresh laundry - 5.0
Pungent	Irritating, nit very pleasant, spicy, sharp scent	Freshly grated garlic - 10.0 Air freshener in the car- 4.0
Green notes	Grassy, fresh vegetables, possible slightly herbal, earthy associated scents	Freshly cut grass - 10.0 Herbal tea - 4.0
Sweetness	Pleasant and sugary scent	Honey - 9.0 Vanilla ice-cream - 5.0
Spiciness	Spicy, sharp scent, peppery notes	Cayenne - 9.0 Dried ginger - 5.0
Woody notes	Brown, deep, warm scent	Wet firewood - 9.0 Pencil shavings - 5.0